

Legal Perspective on Current Income Tax Issues in Myanmar

Htet Htet Z aw *

Abstract

Tax is one of the sources of revenue for the State and government. All civilized countries need to collect taxes for the promotion of their overall economic and social objectives. Tax system is one of the most powerful means available to the government to stimulate and guide its economic and social development. In order to collect the tax and systematically and effectively utilization of collected tax, the laws relating to tax are provided by the union government. In Myanmar, relating to income tax, the Income Tax Law 1974, the Income Tax Rules 2012, the Income Tax Regulations 2012 and the Union Tax Law 2017 have already been provided by the union government. Therefore, a major goal of this study is to analyze methods of defining taxable income, especially methods for deciding what type of income and what part of total profits are to be taxed as domestic income, and what part as foreign income. The issues raised by the “legal provisions” are discussed in this context.

Key words: Income Tax, Assessable, Collect, Legal Provisions, Issues.

Introduction

Tax is the financial charge imposed by the Government on income, commodity or activity. The taxes are collected for serving the primary purpose of providing sufficient revenues to the State, these have become an instrument through which the social and economic objectives of a welfare State could be achieved. They are utilized now for providing incentives for larger earnings and more savings, fostering industrial development by selective concessions, restraining ostentatious expenditure, checking inflationary pressures and achieving social objectives. The power to tax is one of the plenary powers of any government which need not be formally conferred upon it.

In Myanmar, income tax was introduced for the first time in 1974. At present the Income Tax Law, 1974, was amended for five times in 1989, 2006, 2011, 2014, 2016. It provides for levy, administration, collection and recovery of Income Tax. Although the Income Tax Law was supplemented by the amendment law provisions, it still remains the issues in the provision itself.

Therefore, the aims and objectives of this research are to study the current income tax structure and to analyse critically the provisions of Income Tax Law which are arisen issues. This research is bases, analyses and interprets the Constitution and the relevant tax legislations. The research falls within the domain of legal research. Research questions are; why the citizens have the duty to pay income tax; what are the current income tax structure and current income tax laws in Myanmar; which issues are arisen out of the provisions of the Income Tax Law 1974.

Legal Perspective on Current Income Tax Issues in Myanmar

All civilized countries need to collect taxes for several reasons, such as to finance developmental activities, to meet their day-to-day expenses related to maintenance of a free and fair society, to control the economy through fiscal measures, and to a certain extent, to change the economic behavior of people.

In Myanmar like other civilized countries, it is needed to collect the taxes, and in the era of new governments, tax collection system is reformed and enforcement with the effective means.

* Dr, Lecturer, Department of Philosophy, Dagon University

1. Constitutional Duty to pay tax

Under the basic law or fundamental law of the state, the Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar 2008, it is expressly provided the rights and duties of the citizens.

Under Section 389 of this fundamental law of the State, “Every citizen has the duty to pay taxes to be levied according to the law”. Thus, the tax proposed to be levied or collected must be within the legislative competence of the legislature imposing the tax. Further, the law imposing the tax, like other laws, must not violate any fundamental right.

2. Current Tax Structure in Myanmar

In current, although there are eighteen kinds of taxes, duties are levied under four majors heads in Myanmar:

- (1) Taxes levied on domestic production and public consumption
- (2) Taxes levied on income and ownership
- (3) Custom duties
- (4) Taxes levied on utilization of state owned properties,

And it is divided into two types of taxes namely Direct taxes and Indirect taxes. Under direct taxes, person who pays the tax bears the burden of it e.g. Income tax, Wealth Tax etc. while in indirect taxes the person who pays the tax, shifts the burden on the person who consumes the goods or services e.g. Commercial Tax, Special Goods Tax, Service tax, Value Added Tax, etc.

3. Income Taxes

Because income tax is one form of direct taxes, it is imposed on the income of every person whether he is a professional or non-professional. Income tax is charged under the Income Tax Law, 1974. Current Laws relating to income tax are the Income Tax Law, 1974, which was amended for five times in 1989, 2006, 2011, 2014, 2016 and the Union Tax Law which is passed by Pyidaungsu Hluttaw for each year.

This Law shall extend to the whole of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar and shall also apply to all the citizens of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar residing outside the Republic of the Union of Myanmar.¹

The income tax is an annual tax on income levied by the Government. Tax is charged in respect of the income of the financial year (known as the previous year) in the next financial year (known as the assessment year) at the rates fixed for such assessment year in the Union Tax Law passed each year by the Pyidaungsu Hluttaw.

The normal accounting year in Myanmar begins on the first of April and ends on the 31st of March. But it will be changed in coming year from 1st October to 30th September. The return of income for the previous financial year is due in the next financial year i.e. assessment year in which the proceedings for assessment commence, either by filing of a return voluntarily by the income earner or by the Income Tax Department initiating action for calling the return.

3.1 Basic Concept of Income Tax

Every person who has assessable total income in the income year has the duty to pay income tax for that year as prescribed by the Regulations within three months from the end of that year.

Therefore, in order to levy income tax, it must have an understanding of the various concepts related to the charge of tax like the income year, assessment year, income received, total income and person.

Under Section 3 (h) of the Income Tax Law 1974, “Income year” means the year in which income is received.

¹ Section 2 of the Income Tax law, 1974.

Under Section 3 (i) of this Law, “Assessment year” means the year next following the income year;

“Income received” means, under Section 3 (f) of this Law, income received or deemed to be received, or income accrued or arisen or deemed to have accrued or arisen.

“Total income” means, under Section 3 (n) of this Law, the following income received in the income year:-

(i) in the case of a resident citizen or a resident foreigner, all income received within and without the Republic of the Union of Myanmar;

(ii) in the case of a non-resident citizen, all income as prescribed by the Rules;

(iii) in the case of a non-resident foreigner, or a foreigner or a foreign economic organization investing under the Republic of the Union of Myanmar Foreign Investment Law, all income received within the Union of Myanmar;

Relating to the definition of “person” for the purpose of the assessment of income tax, there are of two types, natural person (individual) and legal person (Association of persons). Under Section 3 (j) of this Law, “Association of persons” includes partnerships, joint-ventures, companies, associations formed by individuals, registration of association or institution by existing law, co-operative societies and Government economic enterprises.

3.2 Payment of Tax and Difference Heads of Tax

Whoever has a total income or capital gains chargeable to tax in any year shall be liable to pay income-tax at the time of receiving that income under Section 15 (a).

For the purpose of imposition of tax and the computation of total income, all income, under this Law, is classified under the following seven heads:

- (i) salaries;
- (ii) profession;
- (iii) business;
- (iv) rental income;
- (v) capital gains;
- (vi) income which has escaped assessment;
- (vii) other sources of income.

(i) Salaries

The tax shall be payable by any person under the head salaries in respect of the following income received or receivable by him from his employer:-

- (a) salary, wages, annuity, pension, gratuity; and
- (b) any fees, commissions or perquisites received in lieu of or in addition to any salary and wages.¹

(ii) Profession

Profession means rendering of service for fees with one's skill and includes services rendered for fees by a doctor, a nurse, a lawyer, an engineer, an architect, a film artiste, a theatrical artiste, a writer, a painter, a sculptor, an accountant, an auditor, an astrologer, a teacher, etc.

The tax shall be payable by any person under the head profession in respect of the income received from his profession under Section 10 (a) of this Law.

(iii) Business

The expression "business" includes;

- (a) Any trading business, commercial business or production business and any similar business as well as any services business is included.
- (b) Furthermore, buying or transferring security papers, or investing in security papers to obtain interest is included if such acts are performed repeatedly in a year as an economic business.

The tax shall be payable by any person under the head business in respect of his income derived from business under Section 11(a) of this Law.

(iv)) income received from the leasing of land, buildings or apartments

Under Section 12 (a) of this Law, tax shall be payable by any person under the head rental fees of property, in respect of the income received by letting out land or land and building. In letting out land or land and building, it also includes not a private land or once again of letting out building.

(v) Capital Gains

Capital gain means any profit realized from the sale, exchange or transfer of any capital asset. Then capital asset means any land, buildings and the rooms therein, vehicles and any assets provided as a contribution to an enterprise. In this expression, shares, bonds, security papers and similar instruments are also included. But any inheritance, gift without consideration and donation shall not be included within the meaning of the term transfer.²

The tax shall be payable by any person under the head of capital gains in respect of the gains realized from the sale, exchange or other ways and means of transfer of one or more capital assets within a year.³

¹ Section 9 of the Income Tax Law, 1974.

² Section 3 (r) of the Income Tax Law, 1974.

³Section 13 of the Income Tax Law, 1974.

(iv) Income which has escaped Assessment

Tax under the head of "income which has escaped assessment" shall be assessed on the value of immovable or movable property (including money) if it cannot be ascertained how the respective person obtained this property under Section 14 of this Law.

(iiv) Other Sources of Income

The tax shall be payable under the head other sources of income in respect of the income which is not included under any of the preceding heads of income.¹

Therefore, every person who has income under the above heads of income, has the duty to pay tax in accordance with the rules and regulations of this Law.

Procedure for Assessment

In the assessment of income tax, furnishing of return of income and annual salary statement includes as important part of assessment. So, it is provided in Section 17 and Section 18 of Income Tax Law.

Every person who has assessable total income in the income year shall furnish a return of income for that year as prescribed by the Regulations within three months from the end of that year under Section 17 (a) of the Income Tax Law 1974. Provided that such person who has income only under the head salaries, is not so required.

However, in such a case, an employer shall, under Section 18 of this law, furnish yearly the annual salary statement as prescribed by the Regulations within three months from the close of the income year.

Notice may be served upon any person to furnish his return of income in accordance with the Regulations under Section 17 (b) and whoever, having furnished a return of income, wishes to amend his return for some mistakes in the return, may furnish a revised return before the assessment is made under Section 17 (c).

3.4 Types of Assesseees

Under Income Tax Law 1974, every person who has a total income or capital gains chargeable to tax in any year shall be liable to pay income-tax at the time of receiving that income.²

Here, a person who has received assessable income under this Law and is liable to pay income-tax is called assessee. For the purpose of this law, there are two types of assessee, individual and association of persons.

Relating to individual assesseees, it is also divided into two categories, citizen and foreigner. In these types of assesseees, each sub-divides into two, residence and non-residence.

Under section 3 (p) of this Law, "Citizen" includes an associate citizen or a naturalized citizen for the purpose of this Law and "Non-resident citizen" means, under section 3 (m) of this Law, any citizen of the Union of Myanmar who resides and earns income outside Myanmar for any time in a year.

Relating to "Resident foreigner" under section 3 (k) of this Law, it means that:-

(i) in the case of an individual, a foreigner who resides in Myanmar for not less than one hundred and eighty three days during the income year;

(ii) in the case of a company, a company formed under the Myanmar Companies Act or any other existing law wholly or partly with foreigner share-holders;

(iii) in the case of an association of persons other than a company, an association formed wholly or partly with foreigners and where the control, management and decision making of its affairs is situated and exercised wholly in the Union of Myanmar.

¹ Section 14-A of the Income Tax Law, 1974.

²Section 15 of the Income Tax Law, 1974.

And “Non-resident foreigner” means any foreigner other than resident foreigner in the Union of Myanmar under section 3 (l) of this Law.

Under section 3 (j) of this Law, “Association of persons” includes partnerships, joint-ventures, companies, associations formed by individuals, registration of association or institution by existing law, co-operative societies and Government economic enterprises.

“Company” means, under section 3 (o) of this Law, a company as defined in the Myanmar Companies Act or in any other existing law. This expression includes any foreign economic enterprise carrying on business in Myanmar which is treated as a company by the Union of Government for the purposes of this Law.

Therefore, these types of assessee shall have the duty to pay tax at the time of receiving income.

3.5 Tax exemption and Relief

Although under the provisions of Income Tax Law 1974, every person who has a total income or capital gains chargeable to tax in any year shall be liable to pay income tax, there have also the provisions relating to tax exemption and relief in its provisions itself.

According to section 5 (a) of the Income Tax Law 1974, incomes exempted from income tax are as follows;

- (i) Income achieved by any religious or charitable organization and used exclusively for matters of religion or charity;
- (ii) Income achieved by a local authority;
- (iii) Money from the commutation of a pension, condolences payments (which otherwise would have to be) categorized under the head “salary”;
- (iv) Compensation obtained for death or injury;
- (v) Money obtained from an insurance;
- (vi) Income of casual, non-recurring nature with the following exceptions:-
 - (aa) capital gains;
 - (bb) income from an enterprise;
- (vii) Share of the after-tax profit of an association.

Moreover, under section 5 (b), any person earning income for which the Union Tax Law grants tax exemption, relief or other benefits is entitled to such exemption, relief or benefit.

And under section 5 (c), an exemption from income tax must be granted to newly established small- and mid-sized business for three consecutive years, including the starting year, for income specified as exempted by the Union Tax Law.

If a benefits relating to income tax are stipulated in any other existing law, the benefits must be granted in accordance with these stipulations under section 5 (d).

Relating to tax relief, it has already been provided in section 6 (a) of this Law. According to this section, the following allowances may be specified, amended or added by the Union Tax Law in respect of any Assessment Year;

- (1) basic allowance in respect of an association of persons;
- (2) basic allowance in respect of an individual and allowance in respect of the spouse and children of an assessee.

(b) Deleted.

Then under section 6 (c), the following amount shall be deducted from the total income and the tax shall be computed on the remaining amount of income:-

- (i) basic allowance in the case of an association of persons;
- (ii) in the case of an individual:-
 - (aa) basic allowance;
 - (bb) allowance in the respect of in assessee's spouse and children;
 - (cc) premium paid for the life insurance Policy of an assessee and his spouse;
 - (dd) contributions towards savings funds as prescribed by the Rules.

However, sub-section (a) and (c) shall not apply to the computation on capital gains mentioned under section 13 and to non-resident foreigners mentioned under Section 26.

Moreover, under Section 6-A of this Law, when assessing the taxable income, money donated for any religious or charitable organization sponsored by a state organization of any level or recognized by the Ministry of Planning and Finance of the Union Government by virtue of a notification may be deducted from the amount calculated in accordance with sub-section (c) of section 6. The deductible donation shall not exceed 25% of the total income of the tax payer. In the expression "charity", aid for the public good such as aid towards education and health and aid for the poor and persons affected by natural disasters are included.

Although in the case of association of persons, basic allowance and donations are allowed to deduct in the computation of income under section 6 (c) and section 6-A of Income Tax Law, they may not enjoy this relief under section 23 (a) of the Union Tax Law 2017. Under this section, with regard to the company which is registered and established in Myanmar under Myanmar Companies Act 1914 or the Special Companies Act 1950, 25% income tax shall be assessed on the total net profit before deducting the allowances under section 6 of the Income Tax Law 1974.

But in the case of individuals, under section 20 of the Union Tax Law 2017, the basic allowance under section 6 (c) (2) (a) of Income Tax Law is an amount equibalance to 20% of the income for each type of income. However Total allowances for a year shall not exceed kyats 10,000,000.

Moreover, under section 21 of the Union Tax Law 2017, parental allowance is added to section 6 (c) (2) (a) of Income Tax Law. Under this provisions, the income tax shall be assessed on what remains of the total income after deducting the following allowances in accordance with the regulations:-

- (a) Kyats 1,000,000 for each parents with whom the assessee lives together;
- (b) Kyats 1,000,000 for a spouse;
- (c) Kyats 500,000 for each child
- (d)

4. Issues Relating to the Income Tax Law 1974

Relating to the provisions of the Income Tax Law, there have a lot of issues in the provisions itself. The main issues of this Law are:

- a) Issues Relating to Capital Gains
- b) Issues Relating to Discretionary Power of the Revenue Officer
- c) Issues Relating to Punishment for Concealment

(a) Issues Related To Capital Gains

Under Section 3 (r) of the Income Tax Law 1974, "capital gain" means any profit realized from the sale, exchange or transfer of any capital asset. But any inheritance, gift without consideration and donation shall not be included within the meaning of the term transfer. Then "capital asset" means any land, buildings and the rooms therein, vehicles and

any assets provided as a contribution to an enterprise. In this expression, shares, bonds, security papers and similar instruments are also included.¹

Capital gains tax is applicable to both resident and non-resident as deriving a profit from the sale, exchange, or transfer of capital assets in Myanmar. CGT is payable by the person deriving the profit. A capital gains tax return must be lodged by any person who sells, exchanges or transfers capital assets, even if there is a loss.

If the total value of the capital asset; which was sold, exchanged or transferred, does not exceed 100 lakh kyats, capital gains tax will not be applicable.

The capital gains tax rate for all assesseees (with the exception of those deriving a gain from an oil and gas sectors or a company holding an oil and gas asset) is 10% and is imposed in either Myanmar kyat or a foreign currency.

Under section 5 (a) (6) of the Income Tax Law, it is exempted Income of casual non-recurring nature from assessment of tax. But this rule grants the tax exemption with the exceptions of capital gains. Therefore this rule is unfair for the assessee who got a profit from the sale, exchange, or transfer of capital assets for one time in their whole life. If this sale, exchange, or transfer of capital assets is not for profits or as business and to buy another capital asset, and if the assessee has pay tax, it is not sure that he can buy another capital asset. In this situation, the assessee will try to evade the tax or to conceal the sale, exchange, or transfer of capital assets. This process will accrue to the event of evasion of tax.

Therefore, in order to avoid tax evasion event, it should be the separate provisions of the divide the type of capital gains between Income of casual non-recurring nature and Income of business nature.

(b) Issues Relating to Discretionary Power of the Revenue Officer

Tax avoidance and tax evasion have always existed alongside taxes and will continue to exist as long as there are taxes. In the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, in order to avoid tax evasion, discretionary power is empowered to the township revenue officers for the assessment of the tax under Income Tax Law.

For the purpose of Income Tax Law 1974, the Revenue Officer means the Township Revenue Officer. He or she is the head of the relevant Township Internal Revenue Department who is assigned the duty to assess the tax which shall be paid by the assessee. In his expression, it also includes Heads of the Large Taxpayer Revenue Office and Medium Taxpayer Revenue Offices.

Under the procedure of income tax assessment, every person who has assessable total income in any income year shall furnish a return of income for that year as prescribed by the Regulations within three months from the end of the year.² And if the return of income furnished under Section 17 is found to be correct and complete, income-tax shall be assessed on the basis of that return.³

If the income can be correctly computed from the supporting evidence produced by the assessee, income-tax shall be assessed by the Revenue Officer on the basis of supporting evidence under Section 19 (c) of Income Tax Law 1974.

According to the above provision, it has been arisen the provisional issue in Section 19. Under this Section, the township revenue officer may exercise discretionary power to assess the tax and he or she may request to produce supporting evidence, accounts, and a list of the property that is not included in the accounts. Moreover it may request also the assessee's attendance for the purpose of examination and assessment. Finally he has the power to assess the tax on the basis of available supporting evidence.

In the provision of Section 19, it is not clearly provided that what are the available supporting evidences and the procedures for collecting that evidences. Therefore, it is absolutely depended on the

¹ Section 3 (q) of the Income Tax Law, 1974.

² Section 17 (a) of Income Tax Law 1974.

³ Section 19 (a) of Income Tax Law 1974.

discretionary power of the revenue officer. The exercise of such discretions creates the temptation to abuse the discretionary power of the revenue officer and may also occur the bribery between the revenue officer and the assessee.

Relating to punishment for bribe, section 48 of the Income Tax Law provides that whoever gives and takes bribe or attempts to do so in connection with this Law, shall be liable to be punished under the Penal Law or under any other law specifically enacted for this office. Although it has the provision relating to penalty for taking bribe in section 48, there is no more provisions and procedures protected the bribery between the tax officer and tax payer in the Income Tax Law.

Therefore, It should be further supplemented the rules, regulations and the procedures which limit the arbitrary control and abuse of the discretionary power of the revenue officer.

(c) Issues Relating to Punishment for Concealment

According to the pattern and order of the establishment of criminal lawm the Income Tax Law 1974 also inserts relating to offences and penalty for the breach of this Law. In this provision, it has already provided the punishment for concealment and non-disclosure of the assessee in section 47 (c).

In this provision, if the assessee fails to disclose the particulars within the specified time or discloses less than the income concealed, he shall, in addition to the tax payable on his total income and penalty equal to fifty percent of the amount of tax increase on account of the concealment,, also be liable to prosecution. Then if the Court finds him guilty, he shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend from three to ten years under Section 47 (c).

Relating to punishment for concealment, the maximum punishment, ten years, is equal to the punishment for culpable homicide not amounting to murder under section 304 of the Penal Code. In compare with the offence and punishment between the concealment of the tax and the culpable homicide not amounting to murder to innocent party, the punishment for concealment of the tax is no serious as the culpable homicide.

Moreover, under Penal Code, the maximum punishment for cheating which is the similar offence of concealment is just seven years. So, in compare with these similar offences, the punishment for concealment is more severe than the similar offence of cheating under Penal Code.

Therefore, in order to welfare of the society, it should be replaced more reduced punishment than severe punishment in this provision.

Conclusion

At the present day, many developing countries face many kinds of problems and challenges in the colossal task of tax collection. As any other developing countries, assesseees in Myanmar also suffer in many ways and also face many kinds od problems and challenges in tax collection. To deal with this situation, it must be taken steps to widen their tax base and to reduce the black economy, thereby reducing tax avoidance and tax evasion. It should be replaced and inserted more clearly provisions because the best tax system is characterized by simplicity and fairness. Furthermore, it should be supplemented more clearly provisions that may easily interpreted a guard against injustices because assessment of income tax must be made successfully and depends upon honesty, faith and morality of tax officials and tax payers. Therefore, it may be concluded that it is time to action and improvements fpr effective and successful operation of income tax for future perspectives as well as present needs of economic development.

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References

The Penal Code. India Act. XLV. 1860. 1st Jan. 1909. Burma Code. Vol. VIII.

Income Tax law, 1974.

Law Amending the Income Tax Law, 1989.

Law Amending the Income Tax Law, 2006.

Law Amending the Income Tax Law, 2011.

Law Amending the Income Tax Law, 2014.

Law Amending the Income Tax Law, 2016.

Union Tax Law 2017.

Internet Sources

www.vdb-loi.com